

EDUCATION INSTITUTION ADMINISTRATION FOR VISUALLY IMPAIRED

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Abstract: *The purposes of the study is to do research on the problems faced by the Institution Administration for Visually Impaired. There are 5 groups working, Academic Administration, Personnel Administration, Fiscal Administration, General Administration and Student Affairs Administration. The educational information is given by the school for the Visually Impaired. The grouping interview is chosen and the specialist is chosen by using the semi-structure interviewing, Data Analysis been has done by using the content analysis. The results are: Academic Administration-Teaching activities are non-variety pattern, Evolution 1) process is not agreement with the students' handicap media needs more modernity styles 2) Personnel Administration-Teachers and education officers are not specialized in the subject contents and the necessary skills for the visually impaired, school also needs more teachers to be suitable with the government criterion. 3) Planning and Fiscal Administration: The Government's budgets do not show the reflection of the exactly educational expenses. Besides the costs of teaching technology are also expensive and requested from the foreign countries. 4) The General Administration needs more offensive public relations to the parent government and social community. The School realized the important of education and having a good attitude for the potential acceptance of the visually impaired. The opportunity for studying needs to concern more than sympathizes from their handicap. The personnel information system of the visually impaired overall of Thailand need to create the connection and the integrative between the educational government and develop the quality of life to reach the right of elementary level and an appropriately opportunity. 5) The student Administration-The farther shelters and poor family are the problem to cooperate for developing the student's quality of life property.*

Key words: *Education administration, visually impairment*

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INTRODUCTION

Mankind is complimented as the best human resources and directly responded to the economic and social of the country. The education is an important learning social process to develop the quality of human resource and also being as the instruments for creating an opportunity and an equally human living. However, they are different in the foundation of an economic, social, culture and physical-minded-intelligence. The difference can received equally the right in the fundamental education system, as the disabled could receive the standard quality of education with the appropriate needs of their disabled priceless.

The education for the visually impaired under the social changing of globalization and knowledge based society are caused by the process of the visually impaired school management, so they need for a correspondent adjustment for the article of an education law with the specification by the Education Ministry are decentralized to the Education Areas and the school.

The education administrations for the visually impaired, Thailand, the former years were operated by both from the government and the private school. But overall vision found that the visually impaired still do not have the opportunity and received uncovered the most of education foundation by well done quality. This is because of the insufficient of the mechanical supporting and clearly development, knowledgeable teachers and non technology instruments to develop the correspondent learning with their needs. However the formal school education is necessary to develop for running the education effectiveness. So the clearly the awareness of the present and basic problems of the visually impaired education administration, covered all tasks led to the form of developing administration planning effectively.

METHODOLOGY

The studying of the present and the problem of the visually impaired administration, the director gives the information who managed the education for the visually impaired students. The governments are belonged of 2 places and 7 are owned by the private school, 9 directors and 4 policy specialists or the special education experienced. The administration working frames were setting the administrative content into 5 sections are academics, personnel, budget-planning, general and students. The focus group discussion is applied for the directors and semi-structure interview is applied for the specialists by creating the instruments for collecting information.

- i. Studying the textbook, theory that is relevant with the education administration for the visually impaired students and the policy frame of education for the visually impaired bring to set the content for the conversation and interviewing.
- ii. The specialists appointed the issue of group conversation and the questionnaires followed the frame of thinking with the present and the problems, the policy clues were involved with the visually impaired education administration and also covered with the frame of tasks of the visually impaired school administration.
- iii. Considering the article outline of the group conversation and the questionnaires to study and analyze the present and the problems of the visually impaired education administration, offered the counselor to consider the appropriateness and words checking.
- iv. The adviser suggestions have to improve and correct the content of the group conversation and frame of the thinking those questionnaires to the specialists and bring to study and analyze the present and the problems of the education administration for the visually impaired student.

The researcher collected the information by the methodology of quality researcher and export the information by transforming the tape recorder and content analysis for the conclusion of the present and the problems of the visually impaired education administration go to the synthesizing factor assignments of the developing model for the visually impaired administration school effectiveness.

RESULT

The studying found that the problems of the present condition of the blind school administration are

- i. Academic section
The problem of the visually impaired education is the learning activity by the none of variety teacher, using the inappropriate measurement and assessment for the visually impaired students. Furthermore, the teaching medias are not modernity as the present time for learning development.
- ii. Personnel section
The problem of visually impaired education is the teachers and educating officers are not specialized in many branches of the knowledge and needed more necessary skills for the visually impaired education administration. Including of the quantity of teachers and the supporting officers were not

applied in the appropriate criteria, from the Education Ministry regulations.

- iii. The budget and planning section problem of the education administration about the budget and planning section is the government budget yearly were not enough to manage the medias, technology and teaching aids for the visually impaired student, because of the medias, technology and teaching aids for the visually impaired student are very expensive cost and imported from outside the country.
- iv. General administration section
The problem of the visually impaired education about the general administration is actively action for the public relations to the parents, officials and social community to realize about the necessary of an education, and also having more attitude acceptable with the visually impaired potential to have an educational opportunity or more social opportunity than applied the sympathy for them. Besides, the personnel information systems for the visually impaired overall in Thailand were not quite connected and integrative between the relevant educational authority or quality of life developing for the visually impaired. They keep the right of the basic foundation and the appropriately opportunity.
- v. Student section
The problem of the visually impaired education about the student administration is the farther hometown and hardly connection. Mostly of them were poor so the public relation between the school and the parents are not cooperating to develop with the properly quality of the students.

DISCUSSION

From the academic problem of the visually impaired education administration are the teachers, they need more variety techniques of teaching, inappropriateness measurement and assessment for the visually impaired. The medias and the teaching aids were not modernity as the present time. It caused to the effectiveness of the school administration, we need more method for managing the quality and the standard of an academic section. The personnel administration problem of the visually impaired education administration are insufficiently from the specialized teachers, experts branches teacher of the criteria 1:5 but we are running on the criteria of 1:8. That meant to apply more teachers to create the medias, textbook and learning book for the blind "Braille".

The budget and planning section is the cost per a student indeed disagreed with the present time, the medias and technology and teaching aids for the

blind are all very expensive and mostly are imported from the outside of the country. So the school is necessary to offer the budget from the government and the public organization to join the developing with the visually impaired education.

The general administration section for the blind needed for the active public relations with the parents, social and community. They could realize the necessary of the blind education, handle more opportunity than sympathy them. The blind students can reach to the basic right foundation and more opportunity they could receive. The role of general administration section is to create the cooperating, supporting, promoting and giving the aids facilities to serve all forms of educations beneath the cooperative with the people in the social and community.

The student section for the blind is the variety of hometowns. Because of the farther living places, they also live at school. It would have been a gab connection between the home and school. Besides there also have an extra-ordinary task, It is an active working with the student daily-life supporting both inside and outside the school life in order to do themselves adjustment with the society and environment effectively.

CONCLUSION

The studying of the present and the blind education administration followed the school basically tasks of 5 sections. The problems are quite different from the basic education administration, the condition and the student restricted are tending to have no clues of sight studying. These problems are the cause of the inadequate in textbooks, specialist field teachers and the person per a student budget. The supporting social needed to create the realization to the community and the parents how importance of the education for the visually impaired. As well as the farther hometown, the students have to live at school. It would have been a gab connection between the parents and school.

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